

GolfBiodivers

Data Management Plan

Sandra Rojas-Botero, Frederike Velbert, Pia Tappe, Anna Klopstock, Jens Schaper,
Johannes Kollmann

Version 1.0
February 2025

Gefördert durch:

Bundesministerium
für Umwelt, Naturschutz, nukleare Sicherheit
und Verbraucherschutz

Bundesamt für
Naturschutz

aufgrund eines Beschlusses
des Deutschen Bundestages

Das Forschungs- und
Aufwertungsprojekt

Contents

1	General project information	1
1.1	Title	1
1.2	Acronym.....	1
1.3	Funder of the project.....	1
1.4	Funding ID	1
1.5	Period of the project.....	1
1.6	Project abstract.....	1
1.7	Point of contact.....	2
1.8	Principal investigators.....	3
1.9	Category	3
1.10	Data management requirements and guidelines	3
2	Data description	4
2.1	Data generation	4
2.2	Data reuse	4
2.3	Standards, methodologies or tools.....	4
2.4	Archive of physical objects and description of storage	5
2.5	Data types and formats produced in the project	5
2.6	Data volume.....	5
2.7	Datasets created	5
2.8	Data reproducibility	5
3	Documentation and data quality	6
3.1	Documentation and description of data.....	6
3.2	Methods and tools for data usage.....	6
3.3	Data quality assurance.....	6
3.4	Data quality control responsibility.....	6
4	Storage and technical protection during the project.....	7
4.1	Data storage.....	7

4.2	Backup.....	7
5	Ethics and legal compliance	7
5.1	Management of sensitive data	7
5.2	Copyright and licensing of data	7
5.3	Data sharing restrictions and exclusive use.....	7
6	Preservation and sharing.....	8
6.1	Retaining, sharing, and preserving data	8
7	Creating and loading data for GolfBiodivers	8
7.1	Primary dataset.....	8
7.1.1	Tabular data	8
7.1.2	Multimedia.....	8
7.1.3	Geospatial	8
7.2	Metadata.....	9
7.2.1	General.....	9
7.2.2	Data.....	10
7.2.3	Additional metadata	10
7.2.4	Data structure	11
7.2.5	Variables	11
7.2.6	References	11
7.2.7	Links	11

1 General project information

1.1 Title

Ecological enhancement, monitoring and communication of the biodiversity in Golf courses (English)

Aufwertung, Monitoring und Kommunikation der Biodiversität auf Golfplätzen (German - original)

1.2 Acronym

GolfBiodivers

1.3 Funder of the project

This project is funded within the Federal Program for Biological Diversity by the Federal Agency for Nature Conservation with resources from the Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation, Nuclear Safety and Consumer Protection.

1.4 Funding ID

FKZ 352289405A

1.5 Period of the project

2023–2029

1.6 Project abstract

Severe declines in biodiversity and many ecosystem services in large parts of Central Europe require coordinated action by all land users to improve protection and restore species-rich, multifunctional cultural landscapes. This issue is the subject of intense debate based on recent publications, including the decline in insect diversity, and is the focus of the National Strategy on Biological Diversity. The joint project GolfBiodivers focuses on the landscape-ecological assessment and enhancement of the biodiversity of golf courses as a component of the national biodiversity network with a particular focus on promoting insects. A five-stage approach is planned for the concrete improvement of biodiversity on golf courses in Germany: (i) Landscape analysis of the biodiversity of 32 courses (approx. 1600 ha); (ii) establishment of a kit of enhancement measures consisting of extensively managed meadows, flower strips, edge and woody vegetation; (iii) research of the effects of the 'biodiversity kit' on grasshoppers, butterflies, wild bees, birds and bats, also with the participation of golf club members; (iv) implementation of the results in an enhancement plan for a further 32 courses (approx. 1600 ha); and (v) training of golf course staff, networking with other sports facilities, local authorities and civil associations, environmental education for school classes and public communication work on biodiversity on golf courses. The project is supported by the German Golf Association (DGV,

Wiesbaden) and four (strategically distributed throughout Germany) university working groups (Freiburg, Kiel, Munich, Münster) with corresponding expertise. Quality assurance occurs through professional communication, external evaluation, and an accompanying group of experts. The long-term commitment of the DGV ensures the program's sustainability after the project ends. Agreements with the relevant state ministries and the BfN embed this research-based implementation project in the national biodiversity-promoting strategy.

Abstract in German language (original)

Starke Rückgänge der Biodiversität und vieler Ökosystemleistungen in weiten Teilen Mitteleuropas erfordern ein koordiniertes Handeln aller Landnutzer mit dem Ziel des verbesserten Schutzes und der Wiederherstellung artenreicher, multifunktionaler Kulturlandschaften. Diese Problematik wird auf der Grundlage neuester Publikationen, u.a. zum Rückgang der Insektenvielfalt, intensiv diskutiert und sie steht im Fokus der Nationalen Strategie zur biologischen Vielfalt. Das Verbundvorhaben GolfBiodivers fokussiert auf die landschaftsökologische Bewertung und Aufwertung der biologischen Vielfalt von Golfanlagen als Baustein des nationalen Biodiversitätsnetzwerks mit besonderem Fokus auf der Förderung von Insekten. Zur konkreten Verbesserung der Biodiversität auf Golfanlagen in Deutschland ist ein fünfstufiges Vorgehen geplant: (i) Landschaftsanalyse der Biodiversität von 32 Anlagen (ca. 1600 ha); (ii) Einrichtung eines Bausatzes aus aufgewerteten Flachlandmähwiesen, Blühstreifen, Säumen und Gebüsch auf diesen Anlagen (ca. 100 ha); (iii) Untersuchung von Effekten des ‚Biodiversitätsbausatzes‘ auf Heuschrecken, Tagfalter, Wildbienen, Vögel und Fledermäuse, und zwar unter Beteiligung von Mitgliedern der Golfclubs; (iv) Umsetzung der Ergebnisse in einer Aufwertungsplanung für weitere 32 Anlagen (ca. 1600 ha); sowie (v) Schulung von Golfplatzpersonal, Vernetzung mit anderen Sportanlagen, Kommunen und Verbänden, Umweltbildung für Schulklassen und Öffentlichkeitsarbeit zu Biodiversität auf Golfanlagen. Das Vorhaben wird getragen von dem Deutschen Golf Verband (DGV, Wiesbaden) und vier (strategisch in Deutschland verteilten) universitären Arbeitsgruppen (Freiburg, Kiel, München, Münster) mit entsprechender Expertise. Die Qualitätssicherung erfolgt durch professionelle Kommunikation, externe Evaluation sowie eine begleitende Expertengruppe. Die Verstetigung der Erfolge des Vorhabens ist durch das langfristige Engagement des DGV gesichert. Absprachen mit den entsprechenden Landesministerien und dem BfN betten dieses forschungsbasierte Umsetzungsvorhaben in die nationale Strategie zur Förderung der Biodiversität ein.

1.7 Point of contact

Dr. Sandra Rojas-Botero (Technical University of Munich)

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0366-7383>

sandra.rojas-botero@tum.de

1.8 Principal investigators

Prof. Dr. Johannes Kollmann

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4990-3636>

Email: johannes.kollmann@tum.de

Prof. Dr. Tim Diekötter

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4838-793X>

Email: tdiekoetter@ecology.uni-kiel.de

Prof. Dr. Dr. h.c. Norbert Hölzel

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6367-3400>

Email: norbert.hoelzel@uni-muenster.de

Prof. Dr. Alexandra-Maria Klein

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2139-8575>

Email: alexandra.klein@nature.uni-freiburg.de

1.9 Category

Ecology and environment

1.10 Data management requirements and guidelines

The project is part of the Federal Program on Biological Diversity by the Federal Agency for Nature Conservation (BfN), specifically under the priority area with further measures of particular representative importance for the National Strategy on Biological Diversity (NBS).

This data management plan for Project GolfBiodivers is mainly based on the checklist published by the German Research Foundation (Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft - DFG). Even though the project was not requested to provide a Data Management Plan, this document follows the principles of good scientific praxis detailed by DFG and supports creating and storing research data under the FAIR principles.

2 Data description

2.1 Data generation

- Field observation (by humans, instruments or sensors)
- Laboratory experiments and measurements
- Analysis, derivation or compilation from other data sources

2.2 Data reuse

Generated data will be reused in the frame of the monitoring approach to assess the effects of ecological enhancement measures on different components of biodiversity.

For landscape-scale analyses, the following externally produced data may be used:

- Federal Agency for Cartography and Geodesy (BKG): ATKIS- aerial and satellital photographs, terrain models
- European Space Agency (ESA): Satellite data
- Deutscher Wetter Dienst (DWD): Various weather and climatic data
- European Environment Agency (EEA): CORINE Land Cover (CLC), Copernicus program
- Integrated Management and Control System (IACS): Agricultural spatial data - InVeKoS
Historical aerial photographs from various sources
- Environmental data from databases of relevant German federal states

2.3 Standards, methodologies or tools

Data collection occurs according to sampling protocols defined for the project and comprises:

- Vegetation surveys (plot-based, for composition and structure) following a modified Braun-Blanquet scale
- Collection of soil and standing biomass sampling in the vegetation plots
- Passive sampling of above-ground nesting wild bees, wasps and their antagonists using trap nests
- Passive sampling of birds, bats and grasshoppers using acoustics recorders
- Active recording of butterflies by means of standard transect walks based on the German Butterfly Monitoring
- Active sampling of wild bees using time-based netting routines in the study plots

The consortium members will report additional survey methods implemented regionally in the frame of complementary projects.

2.4 Archive of physical objects and description of storage

Collected insects will be determined, properly labelled and stored in entomological boxes by and, where appropriate, added to own reference collections.

Collected biomass and soil samples will be properly labelled and stored in 50 mL and 25 mL rolling rimmed jars respectively.

Wherever possible, physical samples are retained for up to 10 years after publication of results.

2.5 Data types and formats produced in the project

- Tabular data (csv, xlsx)
- Multimedia – audio and video (wav, jpeg)
- Text (txt, docx)
- Geospatial (shp, others)
- Often, data will be zipped for handiness

2.6 Data volume

Estimation >70 TB

2.7 Datasets created

Estimation >1000 in total for all data types

2.8 Data reproducibility

Part of the study areas where the observations and data collection occur will be modified by implementing a predefined portfolio of ecological improvements, which change their composition and structure and their effects on different biodiversity components. The project follows the approach BACI (before-after-control-impact) for the study of the impacts of interventions on biodiversity responses. Therefore, the areas undergoing modifications cannot produce the same data values in case of data loss. Based on the availability of raw data created under proper standards, processed data is reproducible given the description of processing workflows.

3 Documentation and data quality

3.1 Documentation and description of data

A dataset consists of the primary data, metadata and descriptions of the data structure with defined variables, a reference to other entities (data records, publications), and necessary attachments. The metadata standard is coherent with Ecologic Metadata Language (EML). Mandatory fields of common standards in ecology or specific project necessities are considered and included as required. In the first stage, fields of the metadata are manually filled in a Readme file. The production of metadata and clear data structures are the responsibility of data creators.

3.2 Methods and tools for data usage

All data files are made available by the scientists collecting and producing data in the corresponding institutes and may require certain programs to be visualized (e.g. Excel, ArcGis or QGis). Particular requirements are explained in the metadata.

3.3 Data quality assurance

- Calibration methods in the laboratory
- Creation of Change Log files to document changes in IDs, study site location coordinates, etc.
- Validation of data input and data output: Plausibility checks conducted within each participating university with the produced data
- Proper sampling and collection standards, according to given standardized protocols
- Controlled vocabularies (consistent way of data description) and code lists to minimize errors in data input
- Data verification utilizing descriptive statistics where it applies
- Detailed labeling of variable and record names
- Accompanying notes and documentation about the data specifying versioning of the datasets

3.4 Data quality control responsibility

Data curation concerning data quality is the responsibility of the data creators and the PI at each institute. PIs are long-term contact persons regarding data quality and sharing ('right holders'). Nevertheless, data management support can be found in the central project coordination (data steward), who actively verifies the stored datasets with the data creators, especially caring for high metadata quality.

4 Storage and technical protection during the project

4.1 Data storage

Each institute has local computers and external hard drives, where regionally produced data is initially stored and curated. All data produced within the project is deposited by the data creators in the central tool Sync+Share provided by the Technical University of Munich, specifically in the folder *Data*. In the case of acoustic files, authorized members of the consortium, via account login, deposit the data in the NAS-Server, which the Technical University of Munich provides. Alternatively there is also tape storage from Kiel University with 20+ TB for interim storage. Long-term storage will be organized in relevant repositories for the different data types.

4.2 Backup

All produced data is stored in institutional infrastructures provided by the Technical University of Munich. LRZ Sync+Share (from Leibniz-Rechenzentrum) is accessible to all project partners, contains the project's folder-based documentation, including the research data, and operates data backups centrally. The online Speicher (NAS), accessible to authorized consortium members, allows the storage of large-sized files, namely acoustic files, with centrally operated backups.

5 Ethics and legal compliance

5.1 Management of sensitive data

The project may collect sensitive data. Appropriate methods of anonymisation will be used, as the collection of sensitive data will be subject to prior ethical approval by the ethics committee of the relevant institute.

Indefinite embargo periods are envisaged, as well as the provision of availability to a limited group of people (e.g. for red-list species information on location, contact partners, etc.).

5.2 Copyright and licensing of data

Recommended for all produced data in GolfBiodivers CC BY: Creative Commons Attribution-4.0

5.3 Data sharing restrictions and exclusive use

Data in GolfBiodivers will be made publicly available under a Creative Commons Attribution License (CC-BY). However, an embargo period (exclusive use and access) of three years is anticipated from the end of data collection. Data produced in the project's framework will support the qualification of doctoral candidates and postdoctoral researchers, who must produce scientific publications with a

certain novelty level. Data may be available after a reasonable embargo period during which the scientists have published their contributions. Otherwise, we do not anticipate any implications or restrictions regarding subsequent publication or accessibility of the data (but see Management of sensitive data).

Rules about co-authorship and acknowledgment of the original data collectors and creators are defined. Rightsholders of the produced data are defined and are responsible for the integrity of datasets and, thus, contact persons (decision makers) for issues related to the access and use of the data. Communication of decisions in this regard should be granted to the project coordination and data creators.

6 Preservation and sharing

6.1 Retaining, sharing, and preserving data

Data linked to scientific articles will be submitted before or at the same time as the article's publication. The intended repository is zenodo, with the provision of persistent identifiers (DOI).

7 Creating and loading data for GolfBiodivers

Please bear in mind, that a complete dataset consists of the primary data, metadata with descriptions of the data structure with defined variables, a reference to other entities (data records, publications), and necessary attachments.

7.1 Primary dataset

7.1.1 Tabular data

Typed information collected in the field according to given templates (list). Consider the correct naming of variables.

7.1.2 Multimedia

Audio files collected in a recording period (one folder per recording device per recorded period), downloaded and (almost always) compressed

7.1.3 Geospatial

Files created in individually managed geographic information systems (GIS), geographic information on the sites includes placement of polygons with research and experimental areas, points of location of plots, transects, nests, traps, etc. Contain attribute tables and thus have an own metadata structure

7.2 Metadata

Metadata standards following EML

All the essential information about the primary data will be made available to facilitate its use in the long term.

Structured in sections:

7.2.1 General

Title of dataset

Abstract

Keywords

Metadata creation date (YYYY-MM-DD)

Last modification (YYYY-MM-DD)

Version

License CC BY 4.0 (suggested)

Metadata creator Entity primarily responsible for producing the metadata or the resource described

Data creator Entity primarily responsible for producing the data or the resource described. This entity can be a person, organization, or even a service. The creator is an essential metadata element and is pivotal for proper citation, attribution, and understanding of the resource's provenance

Data collector(s) Person(s)/institution(s) responsible for finding or gathering/collecting data under the guidelines of the project standards, author(s) or Principal Investigator (PI). May also be used when crediting survey conductors, interviewers, event or condition observers, or persons responsible for monitoring key instrument data

Rights holder(s) A university, organization, or researcher that retains intellectual property rights over the dataset

Contact person(s) Person with knowledge of how to access, troubleshoot, or otherwise field issues related to the resource. May also be the "Point of Contact" in an organization that controls access to the resource, if that organization is different from the Publisher, Distributor, and Data Manager. List two persons. Include: name, institute, e-mail

Taxonomic coverage plants, animals, fungi, etc.

Time coverage time format YYYY-MM-DD

date start start of surveying campaigns

date finish end date of survey campaigns

date entry date of data entry (wrap-up)

Geographic coverage

country

state(s)

study sites full name (e.g., Golfclub München-Riedhof, Golfclub Chieming, etc)

Study and sampling design explain, be explicit if adaptations or changes concerning the standardized protocols were applied

Previous data processing explain if applicable (e.g., initial data input in Turboveg)

7.2.2 Data

Dataset type structured_data (table) /unstructured_data (audio, image, text)

Processing status complete/interim_unvalidated

File name(s)

Pay attention to file naming conventions for datasets

- File name should enable disambiguation (unique)
- Distinctive, human-readable
- Consistent pattern (also within folder)
- Avoid ambiguous abbreviations
- Do not use special characters (e.g., * . " / \ [] : ; | = , < ? > & \$ # ! ' () { })
- Underscores between words
- YYYY-MM-DD (after ISO 8601 standard)
- No capital letters
- No "Umlaut" marks or similar signs, transform them (e.g. ä -> ae, ß -> ss, é -> e)
- Maximum length (with pathname) of 256 characters
- Exemplary name YYYY-MM-DD_uni_title_dataset_version

7.2.3 Additional metadata

If the dataset was updated or changes were made, include a free-text summary of changes made to the dataset (e.g., Version 2.1 includes corrected geolocation data and updated plot IDs).

Refer to an external link (a document) – the *Changelog* (pay attention to file naming conventions for the changelog!)

7.2.4 Data structure

File format (csv, xlsx, image, pdf, audio, doc, txt, code)

Delimiter (tab, comma, semicolon, space)

Decimal character (comma, dot)

Missing value (NA can clearly distinguish between zero and missing value!)

7.2.5 Variables

Variables should be organized in the same order as the variables in the primary data, specifying variable description and units of the recorded values

Name identical name as in primary data

Unit appropriate unit, taking care of templates and the actual one used in the field (m, cm, gram, °C, etc)

Data type string, integer, double, date, etc

Description variable description, conventions for binary data or codes used in the data

7.2.6 References

Provide related publications, if applicable

7.2.7 Links

Specify related datasets and documents, refer explicitly to the relevant dataset version.

Specify for example:

- Linked dataset is an older version of the current dataset
- Linked dataset is a source upon which the current dataset is based

List additional relevant files (e.g., files documenting primary data collection and creation like images, documents, and protocols)

List and refer relevant Change Log documents - Version history (documented changes described)